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Mobile Tactical Force Situational Awareness: Evaluation of Message Broker Middleware for Information Exchange

Topic 5: Highly Connected, Automated, and Autonomous Forces

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Abstract

Situational Awareness (SA) is an important aspect of Command and Control, and a key enabler for military sovereignty. It is a critical element for the development of mission command capabilities. Developing SA requires information exchange between a tactical force's elements, including in a mobile scenario. We propose the use of the publish/subscribe paradigm to achieve this.

In this paper, we present our experiments in the evaluation of two publish/subscribe mechanisms - based on Web Services Notification (WS-N) and Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) - applied to a realistic military scenario. Our analysis concluded that WS-N requires more network resources than MQTT to achieve the same functionality. According to our assessment, MQTT was the superior protocol. Furthermore, our evaluation showed that used network protocols, specifically OLSR and TCP, also play a significant role regarding the high use of network resources. In a mobile tactical environment, where network resources are scarce, it is recommended, as future work, to investigate optimisations or even alternative protocols that are better suited for this type of environments.

Keywords — Mobile Tactical Forces, Tactical Networks, Publish/subscribe, Message Broker, MQTT, WS-Notification.

1. Introduction

Situational Awareness (SA) is an important aspect of Command and Control (C2), and a key enabler for military sovereignty (Alberts, Garstka, and Stein, 1999). Recent U.S. Army doctrine has identified several requirements categories relevant to the development of mission command capabilities, including a commander's Situational Awareness (SA) and common operational picture (COP) (U.S. Army, 2013). During an operation, as events unfold, decision makers need to receive the information they require in a timely fashion: on the one hand, soldiers, deployed (or opportunistic) sensors and vehicles generate valuable field information that needs to be disseminated to a potentially large number of recipients, including the Headquarters (HQ). On the other hand, aggregated information - such as a subset of a Common Operational Picture (COP) generated in a HQ - should be distributed to commanders in the field.

The person or system's role in the operation determines the information that it is able to receive, as defined by policies. From a technological viewpoint, a logical approach to support message exchanges from many information producers to many information consumers is through a *publish/subscribe* message exchange pattern. Using publish/subscribe, it is possible to send information from any number of information *producers* to a set of information *consumers* based on their information requirements, effectively decoupling producers from consumers. In the publish/subscribe messaging pattern, this operational need is expressed to the system as an *interest* in a certain type of information, which then drives the information flow.

In our previous work, we have presented a simple proof-of-concept showcasing how publish/subscribe can be applied to a C2 system using smart devices and COTS consumer electronics (smartphones) to generate shared situational awareness between a squad of 9 mobile nodes and 1 fixed node (Manso, Johnsen, and Brannsten, 2017). More recently, we further investigated the use of the MQTT publish/subscribe broker to share information in a tactical environment using a reference scenario developed by the NATO IST124 group. The work confirmed that the MQTT lightweight approach is appropriate for a mobile environment, however, its server-based nature creates a single point of failure that is problematic in disruptive environments (Manso *et al.*, 2018).

In this paper, we continue our efforts by evaluating the publish/subscribe paradigm in a formalized testbed provided by the US Army Research Laboratory (ARL). We perform a comparative evaluation of two publish/subscribe mechanisms - Web Services Notification (aka WS-Notification or WS-N) (OASIS, 2006) and Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) (OASIS, 2015, ISO/IEC, 2016) - applied to a realistic military scenario. While NATO is currently recommending WS-Notification for publish/subscribe (NATO C3 Board, 2011), it has been shown that MQTT is a more lightweight approach to publish/subscribe that may be better suited to the tactical domain (Bloebaum and Johnsen, 2015).

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we discuss different publish/subscribe topologies as well as relevant standards. Section 3 describes the experiments conducted, including presentation of the scenario (and its military relevance), the setting of the testbed (including configuration, broker topology and message publishing frequency) and the choice of broker software. Section 4 presents the results of the experiments for both WS-N and MQTT (with measurements addressing the network and application layers), together with a comparison analysis. We conclude the paper in Section 5 where we present our main findings as well as our plans and suggestions for future work.

2. Publish/subscribe approaches

Event-driven message exchange, or publish/subscribe as it is often called, is a message exchange pattern in which entities that have information they want to share (i.e., *producers* or *publishers*) can publish this information. Information consumers (i.e., *consumers* or *subscribers*) can subscribe to specific types of information they want to receive. When information is published that matches the subscribed interests, it is sent to the subscriber(s). The distribution of information is performed by a *message-broker*.

There are a number of ways in which *subscribers* can indicate which types of information they are interested in when making their subscriptions (Eugster et al., 2003), but the most common approach is basing the subscriptions on so-called *topics*. Topics are keywords that are used to create logical different channels for transmitting information. Information publishers will label their messages with one or more topics, which will be matched to the interests that the consumers have subscribed to using the same topic structure.

Next, several publish/subscribe topologies are presented followed by relevant publish/subscribe standards.

2.1 Publish/subscribe topologies

The general publish/subscribe message exchange pattern can be implemented in different ways and message related tasks (e.g., producing, forwarding and subscription management) can be distributed differently between the system entities based on the chosen *publish/subscribe topology*, which include the direct messaging topology, the single broker topology, multi-broker topologies and brokerless topologies. The choice of topology will impact the level of complexity in implementation of the different roles, on the amount of network traffic generated in the underlying networks, and on the kind of optimizations one can do to the traffic flow to limit the overhead of the solutions. In this section we present the several different potential topologies, including their main benefits and drawbacks.

2.1.1 Direct messaging topology

In the **direct messaging topology**, which is shown in Figure 1, the information producer is responsible for most of the management. An information consumer connects directly to the producer that has the information in which it has an interest and sends its subscription request to that producer. This topology means that the main workload is on the producer, as it is responsible for managing those subscriptions, matching the produced information to subscriptions and forwarding the correct messages to the correct consumers.

Figure 1 - Direct publish/subscribe

The simple structure of this topology results in a tighter coupling between consumers and producers than for the other topologies described next. The consumers need to know, before any communication can take place, which producers exist, which of those producers offer the

information the consumer is interested in, which topics the information is offered under, and how to connect and subscribe to each individual producer. Also, if multiple different producers provide different information on the same topic, the consumers will have to create a subscription to each individual producer. An inherent feature of this topology is that the information producer retains control over how its data is distributed.

2.1.2 Single broker topology

Decoupling the information producers from the information consumers can be done through the introduction of a *broker*, which functions as an intermediary in all message exchanges. The simplest brokered topology is the one in which a single broker is used, as shown in Figure 2. The broker takes on the role of handling subscription management, message to topics matching and message forwarding. In this topology all producers send their topic-labelled messages to the broker, and the consumers send their subscription requests to the same broker.

Figure 2 - Brokered publish/subscribe with a single broker instance

In this topology, the reliance on pre-distributed knowledge is lessened, as the consumers do not need to know which producers exist or where the wanted information is generated. They just need to know how to find and connect to the broker. The reliance on having a shared knowledge of a common topic structure is retained, however.

An obvious drawback of the single broker topology is that the broker becomes a single-point-of-failure. In addition, as all message exchange happens through the same broker node, scalability is likely to be an issue (e.g., a single server only supports a limited number of subscribers and/or messages/interests).

Using this topology, or any other topology that uses intermediaries to forward messages, means that the producer surrenders control of how its information is distributed, which in turn means that there has to be a high level of trust in the intermediaries.

2.1.3. Multi-broker topologies

The single broker topology can be extended to increase scalability and to avoid the single-point-of-failure by increasing the number of intermediary broker nodes. This results in a **multi-broker topology**, as illustrated in Figure 3. There are a number of different ways in which such a multi-broker topology can be structured, ranging from a fully connected mesh of brokers to hierarchies and mixed deployments to segmented topologies where each broker handles a distinct subset of topics. Common to all the multi-broker topologies is the requirement for controlling the responsibilities of each broker (for instance which producers and consumers a broker serves), and to manage the information flow between the brokers (as most multi-broker topologies require messages to flow between the brokers).

Figure 3 - A multi-brokered publish/subscribe topology (represented by a partially connected mesh of brokers)

In a **mesh or hierarchical topology**, brokers are connected to each other and are able to exchange information on a peer-to-peer basis. Similar to the single broker topology, these topologies enable a simple and straightforward configuration of producers and consumers, as each of these nodes only interacts with a single broker instance. Therefore, the information flow between a producer connected to broker A and a consumer connected to broker B relies on proper configuration of information sharing between brokers A and B. This inter-broker information flow can be realised either dynamically or manually, however, dynamic control of the information flow requires inter-broker communication beyond what is covered by the publish/subscribe standards.

In a **segmented multi-broker topology**, each broker is responsible for a subset of the information available in the system. As an example, one broker could be responsible for weather forecasts, while another broker could handle position updates for German forces. In such a topology, producers and consumers which produce or consume more than one information type need to connect to multiple brokers, where each broker represents a single-point-of-failure for its information type (note that it is possible to combine segmented and for instance meshed topologies to avoid this issue). The benefit of using a segmented approach is that the amount of coordination that is needed between brokers is limited to deciding which broker is responsible for which topic subset.

2.1.4 Brokerless topologies

In all the above topologies, message exchange relies on end-to-end connections between the consumer and the entity providing information to the client (either the producer in a direct topology, or a broker in a brokered topology). In a brokered topology, the same is true for the connection between the producer and broker. In a tactical networking scenario, this reliance on end-to-end connections might be too strict.

An alternative approach is to use a brokerless distribution mechanism to realise the message exchange. Brokerless distribution mechanisms include peer-to-peer (P2P) technologies (Skjegstad, 2009) and Information-Centric Networking (ICN). ICN, in particular, are better suited than more traditional end-to-end communications to cope with the non-trivial communication challenges that military operations present (Morelli *et al.*, 2017) as they implement a distributed information discovery mechanism at the network layer without a single point of failure as it exhibits a decentralized broker behavior. Another benefit is that by handling this on the network level, it is more tightly coupled with routing.

2.2 Publish/subscribe standards

There are many prolific publish/subscribe standards, which have been applied to a broad range of applications. For example, the Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP)¹ is much used in the finance sector as a reliable message queue for exchanging high volumes of transactions. The Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP)² is much used as a foundation for chat, but also offers generic publish/subscribe functionality. As such, it has been promoted as a potential carrier for sensor data in the Internet of Things (IoT). Another standard of importance in IoT is MQTT, which currently is more widespread in use than XMPP. Also, MQTT³ is the underlying protocol of choice for popular messaging apps since they require an efficient one-to-many dissemination mechanism for their users. WS-Notification (OASIS, 2006), a SOAP-based standard from OASIS related to Web services as defined by the World Wide Web Consortium, is NATO's choice for interoperable publish/subscribe.

Work by (Bloebaum and Johnsen, 2015) has tested AMQP, MQTT, and WS-Notification in a small scale deployment (3 nodes) using real tactical radios, where MQTT was found to show promise, while AMQP offered reliable communication, but was less efficient than MQTT. (Karagiannis et al., 2015) have performed a survey of relevant IoT data protocols with respect to IoT specifically, where they considered such publish/subscribe protocols as XMPP, MQTT, and AMQP. Also, they considered non-publish/subscribe approaches like CoAP, REST, and Web sockets. Based on recommendations from these studies, we chose to pursue MQTT further as the seemingly best alternative among those protocols tested.

Hence, in this paper we compare WS-Notification to MQTT with regards to performance. For an overview of similarities and differences between these two standards, see Table 1.

Property	WS-Notification	MQTT
Protocol stack	SOAP / HTTP / TCP	TCP
Payload format	XML	Payload agnostic
Quality of service	None built in, but can use additional WS-* standards, e.g., WS-ReliableMessaging	Three delivery semantics: Best effort, At-least-once, or At-most-once delivery
Usage	NATO	IoT, sensor networks, etc.
Topologies supported	Direct and brokered	Brokered
Standardization	(OASIS, 2006)	(OASIS, 2015)

Table 1 - Feature comparison between the WS-Notification and MQTT standards

A notable difference between the two standards is that WS-Notification is based on XML and SOAP, inherently making it a more resource demanding protocol than MQTT which is built directly on TCP. As such, WS-Notification is expected to consume more networking resources than MQTT.

3. Experiments

This section describes the scenario used for the purpose of the experiments, followed by the experimental testbed and the publish/subscribe software used.

¹ <https://www.amqp.org/>

² <https://xmpp.org/>

³ <http://mqtt.org>

3.1 Scenario subject

In terms of military relevant scenario development, the recently completed NATO STO/IST-124 “Heterogeneous Tactical Networks: Improving Connectivity and Network Efficiency” working group has developed a scenario called Anglova that *includes detailed mobility patterns for a battalion-sized operation over the course of two hours, which has been developed by military experts in planning and performing real exercises* (Suri et al., 2016).

The scenario and vignettes include a narrative, mobility scripts and order-of-battle (ORBAT) for several companies operating in a fictitious location of Anglova to conduct several missions. The networks and assets are represented by 243 nodes. Anglova has enabled researchers to study routing in various settings to understand scalability and performance issues of the routing protocol involving highly mobile nodes.

The scenario for our experiments, built based on Anglova, consists in a (fictional) attack involving a mechanized battalion against insurgent’s forces. Specifically, we employ Vignette 2 of the Anglova's scenario limited to one mechanized battalion constituted by 24 mobile nodes (military vehicles) that is part of a Military Contingent coordinated by the Coalition HQ. The battalion nodes are equipped with tactical radios that are used to exchange information. We use nodes' location information and radio signal pathloss between nodes recoded in the Anglova study.

One can anticipate a set of services that need to be supported to give decision makers adequate information to achieve SA. One such service is that of friendly force information (aka Blue Force Tracking (BFT)). Accurate and timely BFT is important to avoid friendly fire, so-called “blue on blue” situations. In the experiments in this paper, we use the NATO Friendly Force Information (NFFI) data format for the BFT service, described in draft STANAG 5527. NFFI has originally emerged to support interoperable BFT in the Afghan Mission Network (IST-118, 2013) and since then it has been successfully used in many contexts. Hence, we consider it a representative standard payload in our publish/subscribe evaluation.

From (Manso *et al.*, 2018), Figure 4 shows the nodes' location and evolution over time. Note that the actual nodes' location information presented in this paper has been modified in order to be unclassified.

Figure 4 - Visualisation of the vehicles' location and history (blue line). Left image: vehicles are starting to move. Right image: vehicles' location at the end of the exercise.

3.2 Experimental Testbed Setup

The experimental testbed used to conduct experiments is the Network Science Research Laboratory (NSRL)⁴ established by the US Army Research Laboratory (ARL). The NSRL provides network emulation capabilities and military relevant data and scenarios for the testing and evaluation of various networking oriented technologies and approaches. The facility has enabled collaboration between ARL researchers and those from other organizations. Additionally, infrastructure in the way of dynamic virtualization has been developed to assist in the execution of experiments in the NSRL. To enable repeatability and scalability of experimentation, ARL has also developed a platform called Dynamically Allocated Virtual Clustering Management System (DAVC). DAVC provides the capability to dynamically create and deploy virtual clusters of heterogeneous nodes as specified by virtual machines.

Experiments are completely reconfigurable through the DAVC interface, with minor modifications to parameters defined in custom scripts (e.g., nodes' location and radio signal pathloss between nodes, as provided by Anglova).

Both the Anglova scenario and DAVC are releasable through NATO collaboration.

The Anglova scenario, incorporating WS-N or MQTT broker messaging services, was setup in the NSRL environment. For that, WS-N and MQTT services were installed onto the Virtual Machine (VM) template of the Anglova scenario to enable the publish/subscribe position location information services. The experiments use the **single broker topology** described in Section 2. The VM template is deployed to nodes during runtime of the scenario. This is illustrated in Figure 5.

For network emulation, we use the Extendable Mobile Ad-hoc Network Emulator (EMANE) that provides – besides the emulation of the radio links – signal propagation and mobility representation to the experiment to create a more realistic environment. The mobility information was drawn from Anglova recorded data.

The emulation allows for various types of routing and radio models to be used; in this scenario we use Optimized Link State Routing (OLSR)⁵ (OLSR 2016) V1 via the olsrd daemon on each virtual machine representing a node in the scenario with wireless links based on the EMANE RFPipe model. The RFPipe model was configured to emulate wideband tactical radios operating at 300 MHz with a 250 KHz bandwidth and 175 kbit/s data rate. OLSR was configured with a Hello Interval of 2 seconds, Hello Validity Time of 20 seconds, Topology Control Interval of 8 seconds, and Topology Control Validity time of 80 seconds.

In the initial set of experiments, we ran the first 30 minutes of the Anglova scenario vignette excerpt consisting of 24 nodes. We set up a DAVC cluster of 24 "Anglova" nodes and one controller node. The controller node is used as the orchestration node and is not represented in the experiment nor does it take part in the scenario. Node 1 for this experiment is arbitrarily established as the broker node (i.e., runs the WS-N or MQTT server). It also has a subscriber service running on it (i.e., subscribes to and receives messages from all publishers). We note that the platform allows for any configuration of broker and subscriber services.

⁴ <https://www.arl.army.mil/www/default.cfm?page=2485>

⁵ <http://www.olsr.org>

Figure 5 - Architecture of network experiment including network emulation, application and scenario layers

Additionally, to facilitate the execution of these experiments, we have created services that launch EMANE and the Anglova configuration. We also have Linux shell scripts that can start and stop the publisher services for both WS-N and MQTT as well as gathering generated pcap and log files.

For our scenario, we set the publishing of the node locations (i.e., NFFI messages) every 10 seconds. In this experiment, we have Nodes 2 through 24 as publishers.

3.3 Publish/Subscribe Software

The publish/subscribe message broker middleware selected for this work includes open source implementations and closed-source software developed in-house at the Norwegian Defence Research Establishment (FFI) as follows:

- For **WS-Notification broker**, we use *microWS-N*, which is a closed-source FFI implementation of a subset of the WS-Notification family of standards. This implementation has been tested for interoperability at the NATO Coalition Warrior Interoperability eXploration, eXperimentation, eXamination, eXercise (CWIX) in 2014. There, we found that the standard functions *microWS-N* offers were compliant with WS-Notification version 1.3, which is the most recent specification (Bloebaum and Johnsen, 2014).

For **MQTT messaging broker**, we initially used the Moquette MQTT broker⁶. However, the broker had issues with deadlocks and race conditions, leading to message loss and the broker freezing up⁷. We then switched to the open source Mosquitto from the Eclipse foundation, which is freely available online⁸. It should be noted, though, that Mosquitto also has some stability issues, notably when used together with transport layer security (TLS) and Web sockets. At the time of writing this paper, these issues are known but still unresolved⁹. So, to ensure the stability of our experiments, we used Mosquitto without TLS enabled to avoid crashes and we made the assumption that security (as in confidentiality and integrity) would be ensured at the radio and network levels (e.g., through IP-Sec or link-layer encryption). Also, we also excluded the use of Websockets in the experiments.

In addition to the brokers, we also needed to implement producers and consumers to use in the evaluation:

- For WS-Notification, we used the closed source client libraries of microWS-N as the basis for setting up subscriptions and publishing data.
- For MQTT, the producer and consumer software were implemented using the Fusesource library¹⁰. Since messages relate to location information periodically produced, the MQTT clients were configured to request at-most-once delivery from the broker (i.e., MQTT QoS=0 that is the most efficient but less reliable setting).

As first described in 3.2, Node 1 functions as broker node (i.e., runs the WS-N or MQTT server) and a consumer node (i.e., runs the consumer software subscribing to all messages). Nodes 2 to 24 run the producer software that publishes a NFFI message each 10 seconds.

As a final remark, it is worth noting that the results in this paper stem from using the above mentioned software and using brokered publish/subscribe with a single broker (see 2.1.2). Using different implementations may yield somewhat different results regarding performance, robustness and stability.

4 Experiments Results and Evaluation

In this section, the results and evaluation of the experiments are presented, with the objective to provide a comparison between the two different publish/subscribe standards (WS-N and MQTT) using a realistic tactical emulation environment (provided by ARL NSRL) based on a relevant military scenario (Anglova).

Our evaluation approach makes use of logging information from both the **network layer** as well as the **application layer**. For the **network layer**, we logged the network traffic via “tcpdump” resulting in “pcap” files. For the **application layer**, we logged the application traffic via a logging interface which we defined by a JSON schema. The logging interface was implemented into the publisher and subscriber services.

For the analysis of the application log files, we used analysing tools from the *Analyse and Test environment (AuT)* project of Fraunhofer FKIE (Angelstorf, Becker, Jansen, and Noth, 2017).

⁶ <http://andsel.github.io/moquette/>

⁷ This known issue is still unresolved: <https://github.com/andsel/moquette/issues/208>

⁸ <https://mosquitto.org/>

⁹ Mosquitto segmentation fault during client connection: <https://github.com/eclipse/mosquitto/issues/406>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/fusesource/mqtt-client>

4.1 WS-N with OLSR and broadband radio links

In this setup, we deploy the WS-N broker *microWS-N* (see Section 3.3) together with one WS-N subscriber on Node 1 (the HQ node). Nodes 2 to 24 (23 nodes in total) each run a WS-N producer software publishing a NFFI message every 10 seconds. The measurements pertaining to network and application layers are presented next.

Network layer

By analysing the network level log files (packet captures) the consumed data rates shown in Figure 6 could be obtained. The figure shows the data rates related to WS-N-based messages and OLSR-based messages each divided into the different protocol layers. The WS-N-based communication consumes 42 kbit/s of the available data rate of the radios (175 kbit/s), which consists of 23 kbit/s of WS-N- (i.e. HTTP-)based packets, 12 kbit/s related to TCP, 4.1 kbit/s related to IP headers and 2.9 kbit/s related to Ethernet headers. The routing protocol (OLSR) generates an overall traffic of 98 kbit/s.

Figure 6 – Consumed data rates of WS-N and OLSR divided into protocol layers

In overall 2955 WS-N-based NFFI messages were sent. The size (application content) of each NFFI message was 1939 Bytes. All messages were delivered. The network logs show that 3594 TCP retransmissions were produced. Most of them were of type “spurious”, which means that a packet was retransmitted, because an acknowledgement arrived too late at the sender and messages are thus unnecessarily retransmitted, which leads to a larger communication overhead.

Application layer

The application logs consist of logging entries of the senders (publishers) of NFFI messages and logging entries of the receiver (broker and subscriber) of these messages. This approach allows us to calculate the overall transmission times of NFFI messages, which represent the age of the positions as observed by the user at the receiver node. The results were analysed with help of analysing tools of AuT project and are shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8. Figure 7 shows as a boxplot diagram the transmission times of all publishers including the maximum values, whereas Figure 8 shows an enlarged view of the diagram showing the first quartiles, medians and third quartiles in more detail.

Figure 7 – Transmission times of WS-N-based NFFI messages (whole diagram)

Figure 8 – Transmission times of WS-N-based NFFI messages (enlarged view)

In all 2955 messages were published. None of these were lost. The overall median was 1.5 s. For each publisher, the median transmission time was between 1.4 s and 1.7 s as shown in Figure 8. As Figure 8 shows, most of the messages were in this time interval. But there are some extreme values which took much longer. For each publisher, the maximum transmission time was between 8 s and 86 s as shown in Figure 7.

4.2 MQTT with OLSR and broadband radio links

In this setup, we deploy the MQTT broker *Mosquitto* (see Section 3.3) together with one MQTT subscriber on Node 1 (the HQ node). Nodes 2 to 24 (23 nodes in total) each run an instance of the MQTT producer software publishing a NFFI message every 10 seconds. The measurements pertaining to network and application layers are presented next.

Network layer

The analysis of the network level log files (packet captures) results in the consumed data rates shown in Figure 9, which were measured at the broker/subscriber node. The figure shows the data rates which are related to MQTT-based messages and OLSR-based messages, each divided into the different protocol layers. The MQTT-based traffic consumes 23 kbit/s of the available data rate of the radios (175 kbit/s), which consists of 11 kbit/s of MQTT-based packets, 6 kbit/s related to TCP, 3.2 kbit/s related to IP headers and 2.2 kbit/s related to Ethernet headers. The routing protocol (OLSR) generates an overall traffic of 93 kbit/s.

Figure 9 – Data rates of MQTT and OLSR divided into protocol layers

In overall 3073 MQTT messages were sent. The size (content) of each message was 909 Bytes (WS-N's size increase was due to extra overheads from using SOAP and XML).

All messages were delivered. The network logs show that 1954 TCP retransmissions were produced. Most of them were of type “spurious” similar to the setup with WS-N.

Application layer

In Figure 10 and Figure 11 the average transmission times of the messages are shown for each publisher in a boxplot diagram. Figure 10 shows the whole diagram including the maximum values, whereas Figure 11 shows an enlarged view of the diagram showing the first quartiles, medians and third quartiles in more detail.

Figure 10 – Transmission times of MQTT-based NFFI messages (whole diagram)

Figure 11 – Transmission times of MQTT-based NFFI messages (enlarged view)

As mentioned above, none of the overall 3073 messages were lost. For each publisher, the median transmission time was between 0.7 s and 0.9 s as shown in Figure 11. The overall median was 0.8 s. As Figure 11 shows, most of the messages were in this time interval. But there are some extreme values which took much longer. For each publisher the maximum transmission time was between 5 s and 92 s as shown in Figure 10.

4.3 Comparison Analysis and Results

A comparison between results obtained with WS-N and MQTT is presented next. The measurements used to support our analysis are presented in Table 2.

	WS-N	MQTT
Network Layer		
Data rate (kbit/s)	42	23
Message size (bytes)	1939	909
TCP retransmissions	3594	1954
Application Layer		
Messages lost	0	0
Delay (median) (sec)	1.5	0.8
Maximum Tx Time (sec)	86	92

Table 2 - Results from Experiments for WS-N and MQTT

From the evaluation of the experiments with WS-N and MQTT as message brokers, it can be seen that MQTT outperforms WS-N:

- In overall (including the whole communication stack) MQTT consumes about half the data rate than WS-N (23 kbit/s vs. 42 kbit/s) of the available data rate of 175 kbit/s which is provided by the radios.
- MQTT generated message size is less than half the WS-N's message size (909 bytes vs. 1939 bytes).
- MQTT caused about half TCP retransmissions than WS-N (1954 vs. 3594)
- Consistently, the median message transmission times measured on the application level were half as large with MQTT (0.8 s) compared to WS-N (1.5 s).
- A few large delays were observed, being the maximum observed pertaining to MQTT (92 seconds) closely followed by WS-N (86 seconds). These, however, seem more related to TCP protocol or networking aspects, and not associated to the message broker.

As expected, MQTT exhibits a "lighter" and more efficient network performance than WS-N, which makes it suitable for mobile tactical environments, where network resources are scarce. Additional optimisations and configurations can be pursued aiming to further improve network performance.

Concerning network-related measurements, it is worth mentioning the following aspects:

- The network captures showed that most of the data rate volume is caused by the OLSR routing protocol (70% and 80% of the data rate for WS-N and MQTT respectively). This suggests investigating OLSR improvements (e.g. different protocol update rates) or deploying alternative routing protocols better suited for tactical mobile environments using wideband (or narrowband) radios.
- TCP assured delivery of all messages. However, the evaluation of the network logs showed that both WS-N and MQTT setups produced many "spurious" TCP retransmits¹¹. This

¹¹ "Spurious" means that a packet was unnecessarily retransmitted, because the respective acknowledgement arrived too late at the sender. Since the congestion control mechanism of TCP interprets "lost" (actually belated

indicates that TCP is not well suited for the kind of wireless networks used in this scenario. Thus, alternative transport protocols should be sought. For example, the use of an UDP-based protocol could reduce the message overhead and increase the utilization of the network bandwidth by eliminating the coordination problems between network links and the congestion control mechanism of TCP.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we have evaluated two publish/subscribe standards (WS-N and MQTT) using the Anglova scenario. The scenario was driven by the ARL NSRL testbed, which offers large scale emulation capabilities. We used a combination of open source software and software developed in-house at FFI to realize the publish/subscribe infrastructure.

The experiments comprised a cluster of 25 nodes, where 24 represented operational nodes (part of the mechanised battalion) and the 25th node functioned as the experiment controller. Nodes were connected by broadband wireless links using OLSR.

Following the experiments' execution, application logs and packet captures were collected and analysed using Fraunhofer FKIE tools and expertise.

Overall, our analysis concluded that WS-N requires more network resources than MQTT to achieve the same functionality. This leads to increased network resource use (about twice compared to MQTT), as well as an increased transmission time (also about twice) of end-to-end messaging. We can conclude, that for the part of the scenario we evaluated, MQTT was the superior protocol based on the considered metrics.

Our evaluation also showed that the used network protocols, specifically OLSR and TCP, also play a significant role regarding the use of network resources: OLSR generated 70% or 80% of the overall traffic for WS-N and MQTT respectively, while TCP produced many “spurious” packet retransmissions. There is a need to investigate optimisations or even alternative protocols that are better suited for tactical mobile networks (e.g., UDP replacing TCP).

It is worth noting that the results observed stem from using specific software implementations. Using different implementations may yield different results regarding performance and stability, though the overall differences between WS-Notification and MQTT should still be evident due to the differences between these standards.

Future work

From the experiments we have seen that MQTT outperforms WS-N in the scenario used. Therefore, we plan to continue investigating MQTT in more detail, evaluating different options, configurations and software implementations (supporting e.g., TLS and what the overhead of security will be in these cases). In addition, since the experiments indicate that TCP is not well suited for tactical wireless networks (wideband or narrowband), we aim to investigate brokers based on MQTT-SN (MQTT for Sensor Networks), since MQTT-SN is based on UDP.

The central nature of the single broker also makes it a single point-of-failure, which must be avoided in a real deployment. As such, future work will cover multi-broker publish/subscribe with different topologies, including investigating where the brokers should be placed in the network. Matching the broker placement with the structure of the tactical networks and the information needs of the users at the lower tactical level can be used to help limit the amount of network traffic. In this context, it will be important to investigate the use of dynamic service

in this case) acknowledgements as buffer overflows, the congestion window is unnecessarily decreased, which leads to a reduced throughput.

discovery (Skjegstad, 2009) to allow publishers and consumers to discover and leverage brokers in a plug-and-play manner, using zero-configuration networking during runtime.

Exploratory work will also be conducted for brokerless topologies (e.g., ICN mechanism) that mainly operates at the network level and does not exhibit a single point-of-failure.

Next experiments will also consider a more realistic emulation of tactical radio networks by using a model which is tailored to specific tactical radios (broadband and narrowband tactical waveforms).

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